

UK Data Service (UKDS) Response to the CoreTrustSeal Curation & Preservation Levels Discussion Paper¹

The UK Data Service would like to thank CoreTrustSeal for their work on this issue and to provide a considered response² based on our internal discussions. We feel that the changes and additions we propose will have broad applicability and value to the community of repositories and data services beyond our own use case.

In brief we suggest that to act as a full information model for tiers of curation and preservation service the actions of setting compliance standards as a condition of deposit, and offering initial time-limited curation (currently level C), should be split to become levels C and D. We would suggest avoiding the term “basic” with reference to compliance (as a wide range of deposit compliance criteria are possible) and avoiding the term ‘minimal’ with reference to curation (for the same reason).

The proposed revision would provide non-overlapping but contiguous levels of service that could be applied across repositories and data services that offer everything from basic storage to full, disciplinary, active long term preservation. All of these types of service are necessary and form part of current research infrastructure, even if the CoreTrustSeal does not currently offer a certification solution for all of these levels.

Even though defining these service levels is excellent progress, we would suggest that it is not sufficient. Despite the value this information has (e.g. as part of repository registry metadata), it doesn't tell researchers and other data or metadata users anything about how a particular object is being cared for. To extend the CoreTrustSeal proposal to support self-describing digital objects we would suggest that the following metadata is needed at the object level depending on the level applied :

- guaranteed and minimum retention periods (not related to level of care)
- criteria set as part of deposit compliance
- criteria set for initial curation
- preservation periods (guaranteed timeframes with start dates)
- Technical preservation information (links to technical monitoring, format criteria, emulation approaches)
- Conceptual preservation information (links to community monitoring, semantic artefacts, ontologies, controlled vocabularies etc)

All of the above should be accompanied by metadata or links to metadata that define whether the repository is providing services at a generic or a disciplinary level as this will impact the expectations for curation and preservation actions.

¹ Curation & Preservation Levels: CoreTrustSeal Discussion Paper <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6908019>

² This paper: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7828046>